

International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation

(A Multidisciplinary, Peer Reviewed and Refereed Journal, Impact Factor 9.13, www.ijmri.in)

Productivity Improvement by DMAIC Tool in Manufacturing Industry: A Case Study

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Abstract

The rapid competition between industries, services or manufacturing requires every industry to undertake a variety of innovations to maintain the survival of its industry. Productivity is a major indicator of industry development. Various efforts are done by the Industry in order to improve the productivity of the company, one of which is the implementation of supply chain management. The DMAIC (Define, Measurement Analyse, Improve, and Control) methodology of Six Sigma has been widely recognized as a breakthrough process improvement strategy for application among human resources that offers an impressive reduction in defects or errors in many industry processes. The Six Sigma approach have been executed in various industrial sectors, which strive to ameliorate continuous improvement, productivity enhancement, reduction Defects and high quality of end products. The present work focuses on analysing and elimination of in process variations causing rejection and rework at different stages of production by using Define-Measure-Analyse-Improve-Control (DMAIC) approach. By implementing DMAIC approach as a problem solving technique the rejection rate reduced from 9.09 % to 5.39 % and rework rate from 12.89 % to 8.46 %. A critical comprehension of Six Sigma relates to its focus on improving productivity, reducing defects, cycle time and lead time in the industrial context of Manufacturing. A company's cycle time is a measurement of their efficiency and a bellwether for profitability and competitiveness. Not easy to reduce manufacturing cycle times, focus on how to reduce cycle time, the expense of additional logistics investment without understanding the value.

Key Word: Productivity, Six Sigma, DMAIC, Cycle Time

1 Introduction

Today's Globalization world, Manufacturers Industry need to find ways to reduce Production time and cost in order to improve operating performance and Product quality. Six Sigma is becoming increasingly popular among organizations from various industries as a set of tools to generate improvement, as demonstrated by the number of large organizations that have taken on the challenge of applying the DMAIC (Define, Measurement, Analyse, Improve, Control) Methodology. A Method for reducing variation, the application of DMAIC in practice can be considered a universal mechanism for problem-solving and process improvement. This study aims to explore the implementation of DMAIC methodology within a student's course semester project in service companies. Insight about the benefits and the challenges of implementing the methodology will be gained. Moreover, we will also identify frequently used tools and techniques within DMAIC implementation.

There are Five Phases in DMAIC:

- (1) Define and value the problem
- (2) Evaluate current performance and determine desired service level
- (3) Analyse causes of problems to discover the root cause
- (4) Improve the process
- (5) Control the enhanced process to ensure the sustainability of the improvement.

Every stage is originally developed through statistical and qualitative tools to attain the designated goal for the respective stage. DMAIC on production process improvement, thus leading to boost the firm's profitability. Six Sigma projects demonstrated substantial cost reduction and intangible gains including better employee morale, teamwork, and productivity.

2 METHOD

In accordance with the DMAIC framework, the project consists of five phases:

- (1) define, (2) measure, (3) analyse (4) improve, and (5) control

The following objectives for each phase:

1. Define: Students identify the most prioritized problem

2. Measure: Students measure the company's current performance and set a specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, time-bound (SMART) goal to be achieved by the end of the semester.

3. Analyse: Students analyse the causes of a problem and perform root cause analysis.

4. Improve: Students propose some improvement alternatives to be implemented, select the best solution, and implement it.

5. Control: Students report the changes that occurred in the business process; if the goal was not achieved, they had to make a Problem Identification and Corrective Action (PICA) plan.

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework for DMAIC Implementation

2.1 Integrating lean and six-sigma

Lean and Six Sigma are two distinct but complementary methodologies for continuous improvement in any organization. Lean emphasizes speed, eliminating waste, and creating

value for customers by maximizing efficiency and productivity, while Six Sigma focuses on reducing process variation and eliminating defects to improve product and service quality, reduce costs, and increase customer satisfaction. When combined, Lean and Six Sigma form a powerful approach called Lean Six Sigma (LSS), which integrates the principles and tools of both methodologies to achieve significant improvements in process performance, customer satisfaction, and financial outcomes. LSS uses a structured and data-driven problem-solving approach, typically through the DMAIC (Define, Measure, Analyse, Improve, Control) framework, to identify and address root causes of problems and achieve sustained improvements. The benefits of LSS are numerous, including increased productivity, reduced costs, improved quality and customer satisfaction, and enhanced employee engagement and empowerment. By embracing Lean Six Sigma, organizations can achieve operational excellence, drive innovation, and gain a competitive edge in their respective industries. The combination of Lean and Six Sigma methodologies offers a comprehensive and systematic approach to continuous improvement, making LSS a valuable framework for organizations committed to achieving excellence in their processes, products, and services.

Fig 2 Cause and Effect Diagram

Six Sigma is a well-structured methodology that focuses on reducing the time and various defects occurring in the processes as well as in the products. Six Sigma methodology was originally developed by Motorola in 1980s and it targeted a difficult goal of 3.4 defects per million. Six Sigma has been on an incredible run over 25 years, producing significant savings to the bottom line of many large and small organizations. Objectives of six sigma: Cycle time reduction, Reduce Variability, Reduce Waste, Reduce Cost, Improving Customer Satisfaction.

Sigma level is a procedure to know the existing condition of a production shop. The calculation of sigma level is based on the number of defects per million opportunities (DPMO). In order to calculate DPMO, three distinct pieces of information are required:

- a) The number of units produced.
- b) The number of defects opportunities per unit.
- c) The number of defects.

$$\text{DPMO} = \frac{\text{No. of Defects} * 100000}{\text{No. of Defects opportunities per unit} * \text{No of units}}$$

Fig 3 Cause and Effect Diagram

S.No	Company	Process Challenge	Tools applied	Outcome
1	Manufacturing –fan production	Inefficient material transport leading to 11% non-value adding time.	VSM	Decrease in total lead time for fan production from 647.94 minutes to 340.9 minutes
2	Window screen production process	Poor plant layout, Ineffective usage of shelf space, Incorrect labelling of boxes , Placement of parts into the wrong boxes	5S	Cost saving of \$45,000 annually
3	Manufacturer and distributor of pharmaceutical products	Inefficient floor space utilization , Long lead time , Poor inventory management	5 Whys, VSM	38% reduction in storage area and 50% reduction in production staff.
4	Electronics industry	Poor inventory management , Waste and bottlenecks ,Unorganized workplace	ABC analysis, 5S, DMAIC, Cause and Effect, PDCA and VSM	30.4% reduction in lead time and thus increasing the production rate by 24%.
5	Healthcare - Hospitals in Ireland	Non availability of medical records at the required time and place , Increased cases of patients falling in the hospital	5S, Root Cause analysis, Process Mapping, Control Chart, Load levelling, Checklist, seven wastes	Introduction of mistake proofing practices to prevent fall occurrences, Reduction in the lead time of administering clozapine from 14 days to 4 days
6	Printing Company	Failure in meeting demand caused by poor setup of the machines	Root cause analysis, Value stream mapping, time study	Productivity improvement from 2,609 impression/hour to 3,300 impression/hour (20.93% increase) in the printing machine
7	Biopharmaceutical	Improvement of current process and reduction of current cycle time	Value stream mapping (current and future state), SIPOC Diagram, CTQ, Root Cause analysis	Reduction in process cycle time from 1312 min to 595.5 min
8	Agriculture	Field failure of tractor assembly	SIPOC, Fishbone, New	90% reduction in field failure rate , Cost savings of 3.36 million Indian Rupees per annum
9	Food processing	Process Improvement drive to reduce variation in weightage of products	Control charts, Root cause analysis	40% reduction in rejection rate of milk powder pouch, Projected annual savings of 7,000,000 Indian Rupees.
10	Information Technology	Adoption of Lean Six Sigma to the Information Technology Infrastructure Library (ITIL) framework for process improvement	PDCA, DMAIC, ITIL, UAT	Improvement in sigma level of defective tickets from 1.83 to 2.2 Sigma § Elimination of waste by reducing team size from 31 to 24

11	Aerospace	Challenges with production capacity and capability	Value stream mapping, QFD chart, Single Minute Exchange of Die (SMED)	7% reduction in the time it takes for value added activities, 43.5% reduction in time it takes for non-value-added activities
12	Higher Education	Increasing customer satisfaction in the University computer center	5 why, value stream mapping, Control chart	Satisfaction level of customers improved from 2.29 to 4.1 on a scale of 1-6, Annual cost savings of 360,000 Indian rupees ,Positive feedback from end users
13	Banking and finance	High cost per employee , Low service quality	VSM	lower wait time for customers and ,lower stress levels for employees, increased customer satisfaction , More profit and business

Fig 4 Lean versus Six Sigma: Selection criteria

2.2 CYCLE TIME

The time required at each station for the performance of the work is known as cycle time. Cycle time is normally larger than the service time. The cycle time at a station is the time interval between the completion or the starting of work on successive items, and, therefore includes both productive and non - productive work as well as any idle time.

$$\text{Cycle Time} = \text{Service Time} + \text{Idle Time}$$

$$\text{Cycle Time, } C = \frac{\text{Useful Production Time Per day}}{\text{Output per day}}$$

$$C = T/Q$$

Fig 5 Yield Cycle Time

Cycle Time: The Time to complete a task or collection of tasks.

Throughput: The desired process throughput is inverse takt time.

Yield: The amount of product during a processing cycle.

TYPE	IMPROVEMENT PLAN SUGESSTED
MEN	Must have skill/training-Knowledge. Must have good attitude/pay full attention. Follow work procedure properly.
MATERIAL	Every incoming material must be properly handled. Standardization and specification
METHOD	Proper process and Tooling Light should be proper.
MACHINE	A preventive maintenance ensure machine always in good condition.

2.3 Advantages of Reduced Cycle Time

- More responsive to changing customer demands.
- Quicker time to market with new products.
- Save money by reducing WIP (Work in progress)
- Increase yield
- Quicker feedback for the process development and process capability improvement programs.

➤ Additional savings through incremental improvements:

a. Improved employee productivity, which means savings if fewer employees are needed or increased factory output if consistent with factory goals.

b. Improved equipment utilization by being smarter about maintenance, set ups, production tests, balance, etc.

c. Reduced non-productive tests and process control measurements.

Table 1 Number of Rejection and Rework units per week before Improvement

Week No.	Total Production	Rejection	%	Rework	%
1	562	52	9.25	75	13.34
2	547	48	8.77	79	14.44
3	585	59	10.08	68	11.62
4	523	41	7.84	75	14.34
5	577	55	9.53	62	10.74
	Total= 2794		Average= 9.09 %		Average= 12.89 %

Fig 6 Graph for Rejection units per Week before Improvement

Fig 7 Graph for Rework units per Week before Improvement

Table 2 Number of Rejection and Rework units per Week after Improvement

Week No.	Total Production	Rejection	%	Rework	%
1	576	35	6.07	51	8.85
2	578	36	6.22	58	10.03
3	571	31	5.43	43	7.53
4	582	28	4.81	48	8.24
5	585	26	4.44	45	7.69
	Total= 2892		Average = 5.39 %		Average = 8.46 %

Fig 8 Graph for Rejection units per week after Improvement

Fig 9 Graph for Rejection units per week after Improvement

Fig 10 Graph for Average (%) Rejection units per week before Improvement

Fig 11 Graph for Average (%) Rework units per week after Improvement

3 Conclusion

This paper presented a research work on Reduction in process cycle time in manufacturing industry. The Six Sigma approach have been executed in various industrial sectors, which strive to ameliorate continuous improvement, productivity enhancement, reduction Defects and high quality of end products. The present work focuses on analysing and elimination of in process variations causing rejection and rework at different stages of production by using Define-Measure-Analyse-Improve-Control (DMAIC) approach. Implementing DMAIC approach as a problem solving technique the rejection rate reduced from 9.09 % to 5.39 % and rework rate from 12.89 % to 8.46 %. A critical comprehension of Six Sigma relates to its focus on improving productivity, reducing defects, cycle time and lead time in the industrial context of Manufacturing. A company's cycle time is a measurement of their efficiency and a bellwether for profitability and competitiveness.

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